

A hypothetical point-mass rotation powered by the gravitational potential energy and photons

Zhe Lu

November 18, 2022

Abstract. The amount of work of a hypothetical rotating point-mass is evaluated in units of gravitational potential energy and photon energy. As specifications of the rotational motion, the value of rotational angle is set to be proportional to 2π in radian, the length of radius of rotation, which is defined as the ratio of circumference to 2π , be proportional to the geometric-constant golden-ratio φ , and the constant amount of the tangential component of force be proportional to the constant e . Then, the amount of rotational work would be proportional to $2\pi\varphi e J$. The units of gravitational potential energy and photon energy on the same magnitude are set, according to the significant digits of the physical constants G and h , as $G \times 10^{11} kg^2 m^{-1} = 6.674 J$ and $h \times 10^{34} s^{-1} = 6.626 J$, respectively. When evaluated on the basis of four significant digits, the sum of these two types of energy together turns out to be related to $2\pi\varphi e J$ by a scalar, i.e., $\ln\varphi$, such that $G \times 10^{11} kg^2 m^{-1} + h \times 10^{34} s^{-1} = 2\pi\varphi e \ln\varphi J$.

Introduction

Gravitational and electromagnetic interactions are two types of fundamental interactions, which are commonly experienced in daily life and can be used to produce mechanical work. Derived from Newton's law, the gravitational potential energy between two bodies with the masses M_1 and M_2 separated by a distance of r between their centers of mass is given by

$$U_G = -G \frac{M_1 M_2}{r} \quad (1)$$

where G ($6.674 \times 10^{-11} kg^{-1} m^3 s^{-2}$) is the Newtonian constant of gravitation [1,2]. In the Planck relation, the electromagnetic energy carried by a photon is expressed as

$$E_h = h\nu \quad (2)$$

where h ($6.626 \times 10^{-34} kg m^2 s^{-1}$) is Planck's constant [2,3], and ν is the frequency of the photon.

Below, an evaluation of the amount of rotational work that is equivalent to the sum of specific amounts of U_G and E_h is described. The entire evaluation is done on the basis of four significant digits. Summaries of other related studies have already been shared [4-7].

Evaluation

For operational simplicity, the amounts of gravitational potential energy and photon energy on the same magnitude are specified, according to the significant digits of G and h , as

$$U_G = G \frac{M_1 M_2}{r} = G \times 10^{11} kg^2 m^{-1} = 6.674 J \quad (3)$$

and

$$E_h = h\nu = h \times 10^{34} s^{-1} = 6.626 J. \quad (4)$$

The sum of these two types of energy (E_S) is expressed as

$$E_S = U_G + E_h = G \times 10^{11} kg^2 m^{-1} + h \times 10^{34} s^{-1} = 13.30 J. \quad (5)$$

The quantities that specify the amount of rotational work (W_R), equivalent to E_S , are set such that the value of rotational angle (θ) is proportional to 2π in radian, the length of radius (R) of rotation, which is defined as the ratio of circumference to 2π , is proportional to the geometric-constant golden-ratio φ , and the constant magnitude of the tangential component of force ($F_{\parallel}$) is proportional to the constant e . As such, W_R is expressed as

$$W_R = \theta R |F_{\parallel}| = 2\pi\varphi e \alpha J \quad (6)$$

where α is a scalar to be determined.

Now, let's set W_R and E_S to be equal:

$$W_R = E_S. \quad (7)$$

Substituting Eqs. 5 and 6 into Eq. 7 yields

$$2\pi\varphi e \alpha J = G \times 10^{11} kg^2 m^{-1} + h \times 10^{34} s^{-1} = 13.30 J. \quad (8)$$

For operational convenience, α is solved, first in the forms of e^α through the following apparent numerical relation:

$$(e^\alpha)^2 - e^\alpha = \left(e^{\frac{13.30}{2\pi\varphi e}} \right)^2 - e^{\frac{13.30}{2\pi\varphi e}} = e^{\frac{2 \times 13.30}{2 \times 3.142 \times 1.618 \times 2.718}} - e^{\frac{13.30}{2 \times 3.142 \times 1.618 \times 2.718}} = 1.000 \quad (9)$$

which corresponds to the quadratic equation for solving the geometric-constant golden-ratio φ ,

$$\varphi^2 - \varphi = 1 \quad (10)$$

whose solutions are

$$\varphi = \frac{1 \pm \sqrt{5}}{2}. \quad (11)$$

The positive solution is the non-transcendental, irrational number 1.618..., and is adopted here. Adopting the positive solution leads to

$$e^\alpha = \varphi \quad (12)$$

and then

$$\alpha = \ln\varphi \quad (13)$$

Substituting Eq. 13 into Eq. 8 gives

$$2\pi\varphi e \ln\varphi J = G \times 10^{11} \text{kg}^2 \text{m}^{-1} + h \times 10^{34} \text{s}^{-1} = 13.30 J \quad (14)$$

For reference, the expression for calculating energy from the Boltzmann entropy is

$$E_B = T k_B \ln W \quad (15)$$

where W is the so-called thermodynamic probability, T is the absolute temperature in the unit K , and k_B is the Boltzmann constant, equaling $1.381 \times 10^{-23} \text{J K}^{-1}$, compared with the value of $\pi\varphi e = 13.82$.

Given the mathematical relations

$$\ln\varphi = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{j\varphi^{2j}} \quad (16)$$

and

$$\ln\varphi = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2j\varphi^j} \quad (17)$$

where $j = 1, 2, 3 \dots$ [8] (for Eq. 17 see Appendix), the product $2\pi\varphi e \ln\varphi$ in Eq. 14 may be expressed with the series as

$$2\pi\varphi e \ln\varphi = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{2\pi\varphi e}{j\varphi^{2j}} \quad (18)$$

or

$$2\pi\varphi e \ln\varphi = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{\pi\varphi e}{j\varphi^j}. \quad (19)$$

On the basis of Eq. 18 or 19, the value of the total work specified by $2\pi\varphi e \ln\varphi$ would equal that of the sum of a series of rotational motion, which is expressed as

$$W_R = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} W_{Rj} = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{2\pi\varphi e}{j\varphi^{2j}} J = G \times 10^{11} \text{kg}^2 \text{m}^{-1} + h \times 10^{34} \text{s}^{-1} \quad (20)$$

or

$$W_R = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} W_{Rj} = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{\pi \varphi e}{j \varphi^j} J = G \times 10^{11} \text{kg}^2 \text{m}^{-1} + h \times 10^{34} \text{s}^{-1} \quad (21)$$

Discussion

In a previous study, the mean internal energy (U_{int}) of a hypothetical thermodynamic system, which has no free energy, was evaluated [7]. The energy levels of the system are spaced in the following pattern,

$$E_i = (2i + 1)E_0 \quad (22)$$

($i = 0, 1, 2, 3 \dots$), which formulaically resembles the energy eigenvalues for the solution of the time-independent Schrödinger equation for a quantum harmonic oscillator [9]. In the framework of the Maxwell-Boltzmann statistics, the probability (p_i) of the energy state i is given by

$$p_i = \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \quad (23)$$

which is self-normalized in the following infinite geometric series

$$\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} = 1. \quad (24)$$

Thus, the system is equivalent to a probability space with infinite, asymmetric partitions. When U_{int} is evaluated as the sum of the weighted energy of individual states, effectively in the form of the Gibbs entropy, the evaluation yields

$$U_{int} = -\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} p_i \ln p_i = -\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} = \frac{1}{\beta} \left(\varphi + \frac{1}{\varphi} \right) \ln \varphi \quad (25)$$

in which thermodynamic $\beta = \frac{1}{k_B T}$.

Relating Eq. 14 to Eq. 25 gives

$$2\pi \varphi e \ln \varphi J = \frac{1}{\beta} \left(\varphi + \frac{1}{\varphi} \right) \ln \varphi \quad (26)$$

rearranged to

$$\beta = \frac{\left(\varphi + \frac{1}{\varphi} \right) \ln \varphi}{2\pi \varphi e \ln \varphi J} = \frac{\varphi + \frac{1}{\varphi}}{2\pi \varphi e J} = \frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \varphi}{2\pi \varphi e J} = \frac{1.382 \varphi}{2 \times 13.82 J} = \frac{\varphi}{20} J^{-1}. \quad (27)$$

A combination of Eqs. 14 and 25-27 yields

$$-\frac{20}{\varphi} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} J = 2\pi\varphi e \ln \varphi J = G \times 10^{11} \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1} + h \times 10^{34} \text{ s}^{-1} \quad (28)$$

or

$$-\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} J = \frac{1}{10} \pi \varphi^2 e \ln \varphi J = \frac{\varphi}{2} (G \times 10^{10} \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1} + h \times 10^{33} \text{ s}^{-1}) \quad (29)$$

Thus, the partition of a probability space in accordance of Eq. 24 would yield energy or support work in an amount of $\frac{1}{10\beta} \pi \varphi^2 e \ln \varphi$, equivalent to $\frac{\varphi}{2\beta J} [G \times 10^{10} \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1} + h \times 10^{33} \text{ s}^{-1}]$, in the latter of which $\frac{1}{\beta J}$ merely serves as a scalar variable. Conversely, on the basis of the first and second laws of thermodynamics, the same amount of work would be required to eliminate the partitions and restore the unity probability space, on the expense of a rise in entropy elsewhere.

Relating Eq. 16 or 17 to Eq. 29 gives

$$-\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} = \frac{1}{10} \pi \varphi^2 e \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{j\varphi^{2j}} \quad (30)$$

or

$$-\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} = \frac{1}{20} \pi \varphi^2 e \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{j\varphi^j} \quad (31)$$

rearranged to

$$-\frac{\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}}}{\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{j\varphi^{2j}}} = \frac{1}{10} \pi \varphi^2 e \quad (32)$$

or

$$-\frac{\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}}}{\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{j\varphi^j}} = \frac{1}{20} \pi \varphi^2 e. \quad (33)$$

Thus, in terms of the total amount of energy, the energy distribution specified by

$-\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}}$ is equivalent to that specified by $\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{\pi \varphi^2 e}{10j\varphi^{2j}}$ or $\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{\pi \varphi^2 e}{20j\varphi^j}$, i.e.,

$$-\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} = \frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{\pi \varphi^2 e}{10j\varphi^{2j}} \quad (34)$$

or

$$-\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} = \frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{\pi \varphi^2 e}{20j\varphi^j} \quad (35)$$

Similar to what was stated above, the last part in Eq. 34 or 35 might be viewed as an expression of the total work associated with a series of rotational motion defined by $\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{\pi \varphi^2 e}{10j\varphi^j}$ or $\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{\pi \varphi^2 e}{20j\varphi^j}$, in which $\frac{1}{\beta}$ serves as a scalar variable with the unit J .

Appendix

The following relation [8],

$$-\ln\left(1 - \frac{1}{\varphi}\right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n\varphi^n} \quad (36)$$

may be re-expressed as

$$-\ln\left(\frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n\varphi^n} \quad (37)$$

and then rearranged to

$$\ln\varphi = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2n\varphi^n}. \quad (38)$$

References

1. Tiesinga, E., Mohr, P.J., Newell, D.B. and Taylor, B.N. CODATA recommended values of the fundamental constants: 2018. *Review of Modern Physics* 93: 025010-1-63, 2021.
2. 2018 CODATA Value: Newtonian constant of gravitation. *The NIST Reference on Constants, Units, and Uncertainty*. NIST. Retrieved on September 27, 2022. <https://www.physics.nist.gov/cgi-bin/cuu/Value?bg>
3. 2018 CODATA Value: Planck constant. *The NIST Reference on Constants, Units, and Uncertainty*. NIST. Retrieved on September 27, 2022. https://www.physics.nist.gov/cgi-bin/cuu/Value?h|search_for=h
4. Lu, Z. Lu, Z. An apparent relation between the Newtonian gravitational constant and the Planck constant in a geometry-based energetic expression derived from a hypothetical system. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7126702>, 2022.
5. Lu, Z. Apparent relations between the physical constants G, h and k and physical units. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6654172>, 2022.
6. Lu, Z. An apparent relation between the Newtonian gravitational constant and the Planck constant in a geometry-based energetic expression derived from a hypothetical system. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7126702>, 2022.
7. Lu, Z. Mean energy in hypothetical systems with an infinite number of equally spaced energy levels. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7255734>, 2022.
8. Brown, C. The natural logarithm of the golden section. *Fibonacci Quart.* 55(5): 42-44, 2017.
9. Blaise, Z., Henri-Rousseau, O. 2011. *Quantum oscillators*. Wiley.